

Anti-corrosive properties of *Urena lobata* leaves extract for mild steel in 0.5 M H₂SO₄: Electrochemical and Spectroscopic studies

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Abstract

Corrosion inhibition potential of *Urena lobata* leaves extracts (ULLE) were carried out using electrochemical and spectroscopic methods. Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS) revealed that charge transfer resistance (R_{ct}) increased from 386.4 – 984.5 Ω cm² while the capacitance of double-layer (C_{dl}) decreased from 4.8 – 3.2 μ F cm⁻² with increasing ULLE concentration from 0.2 – 1.0 g/L. The decreased in C_{dl} values with increase in concentration was due to the increase in the surface coverage by the inhibitor which resulted in an increase in the inhibition efficiency. Potentiodynamic polarization (PDP) showed the maximum range of shift in corrosion potential (E_{corr}) values is 52.1 mV which suggested that ULLE acts as mixed type inhibitor that is predominantly cathodic due to the higher the values of Tafel cathodic slopes (β_c) over those of the anode (β_a). UV-Visible spectroscopy (UV-Vis) and GC-MS results revealed the presence of organic compounds in the inhibitor which were responsible for the extracts' ability to inhibit corrosion of mild steel. The inhibition process followed physisorption with Langmuir R-squared values (R^2) of 0.9983 and 1.0000 for PDP and EIS respectively. Thermodynamic parameters showed that the adsorption of inhibitor on the mild steel surface was feasible, spontaneous and exothermic.

Keywords: Corrosion inhibition, electrochemical studies, *Urena lobata*, mild-steel, extract.

1. Introduction

Metal corrosion is inevitable in the environment. Various protective measures are being taken to prevent the corrosion of metals of which inhibitors are very effective [1]. An inhibitor is a chemical substance which is added in a small concentration to a corrosive environment to decrease the corrosion rate. A small portion of inhibitors is added continuously or intermittently to the cleaning solvents like pickling acids, acid

stimulation fluids, cooling waters, and oil and gasoline line production streams to control corrosion. To protect the metals from an aggressive environment, many organic compounds having one or more heteroatoms on their chemical structure mainly nitrogen have been studied and employed as corrosion inhibitors [2].

Corrosion inhibitors are either synthetic or natural chemicals. Interest in synthetic compounds as corrosion inhibitor is diminishing because they are often expensive and persist in the environment when utilized. Hence, natural products are widely used as alternative corrosion inhibitor in place of synthetic ones [3]. Extracts from plant parts such as *Euphoria royleana* [4], *Enantia Chlorantha* [5], *Rhynchosyilis retusa* [6], *Olox subscorpioidea* [7], etc have been utilized as corrosion inhibitors for metal corrosion. Plant extracts like other natural products are cheap, biodegradable and do not contain heavy metals or other toxic compounds [8].

Corrosion inhibition properties of plant extracts are due to the presence of various phytochemical molecules like tannins, alkaloids, saponins, flavonoids, etc [9-10]. These metabolites usually bear polar functional group-containing nitrogen, sulphur, or oxygen as heteroatoms, as well as triple or double conjugate bonds which act as major absorption centres on the surface of the metal. The lone pair of electrons in heteroatoms or π -electrons in conjugate bonds is responsible for the formation of adsorption film layers over mild steel materials [4][11]. In this present study, *Urena lobata* leaf extract which contains saponins, flavonoids, tannins etc [12] will be utilized as an inhibitor of mild steel corrosion in 0.5 M H₂SO₄ solution.

2. Experimental

2.1 Materials preparation

Fresh *Urena lobata* leaves were obtained from Farms in Aluu, Port Harcourt, Nigeria. The leaves were washed under running tap, dried to constant weight under shade and ground into fine powder. The stock solution of leaves extract was prepared by soaking a 500 g of dry leaves powder in 1000 g of methanol for 72 hours. The resulting solution was filtered thrice and a dark green filtrate was obtained. The filtrate was concentrated using rotatory evaporator to obtain the methanolic leaves extract of *Urena lobata* (ULLE) which is used as the inhibitor for this study. Desired concentrations of the inhibitor's solutions were prepared by measuring accurate amount of the inhibitor and diluting with appropriate amount of 0.5 M H₂SO₄.

The mild steel sheet for this study was obtained from Metal section of Mile 3 Market, Port Harcourt, Nigeria. The sheet was 1.5 mm in thickness and were mechanically pressed cut into 2 cm x 3 cm coupons. These coupons were used as cut without further polishing.

The coupons were degreased in ethanol, dried in acetone and stored in moisture free desiccators before their use in corrosion studies. The weight percentage composition of the mild steel is: C (0.2300), Mn (0.2654), Cr (0.0528), Co (0.0313), Ni (0.2205), Cu (0.2120), Mo (0.0330), Si (0.0547) and the rest Fe.

2.2 ULLE Inhibitor Characterization

UV-visible spectrophotometry

Uv-visible spectrophotometric analysis was conducted on the ULLE extract using a UV-visible spectrophotometer (Shimadzu Model 240) with a slit width of 2 nm, using a 10-mm cell at room temperature.

Gas Chromatography – Mass Spectrophotometry (GC-MS)

This analysis was performed on the ULLE using GC model: 7890A Agilent Technologies and MS model: 5975C Agilent Technologies coupled with a HP-5 capillary fused silica column (30 m x 320 μm x 0.25 μm). The temperature was programmed as follows: Initial temperature was 60 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (isothermal for 4 minutes), final temperature of 310 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (isothermal for 5 minutes). Other operating conditions were as follows: Carrier gas is helium (99.999%), Pressure 3.1325 Psi, flow rate 1.626 ml/min, average velocity 46.699 cm/sec.

3. Results And Discussion

3.1 Potentiodynamic Polarization Studies

Potentiodynamic polarization curves for corrosion inhibition of mild steel in the absence and presence of different concentrations of the inhibitors ULLE are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Potentiodynamic polarization curves for mild steel in absence and presence of different concentration of ULLE

Figure 1 shows the potentiodynamic polarization curves for mild steel dissolution in 0.5 M H_2SO_4 in the absence and presence of different concentrations of ULLE inhibitor at 303 K. The numerical values of the variation of corrosion current density (I_{corr}), corrosion potential (E_{corr}), Tafel slopes (β_a and β_c), degree of

surface coverage (θ) and inhibition efficiency (% IE) with the concentrations of the ULLE inhibitor are given in Table 1.

Table 1: Potentiodynamic polarization parameters for mild steel in 0.5 M H₂SO₄ solution in the presence and absence of the inhibitor

Concentration g/L	E _{corr} mV/SCE	I _{corr} μAcm ⁻²	β _a mVdec ⁻¹	β _c mVdec ⁻¹	θ	IE %
0.0	-467.1	594.0	64.7	67.8	-	-
0.2 g/L	-442.2	143.4	79.7	157.8	0.760	76
0.6 g/L	-434.5	32.2	51.2	137.6	0.946	95
1.0 g/L	-415.0	10.1	21.5	98.0	0.983	98

The results indicated that the cathodic and anodic curves obtained exhibit mixed-type behavior. Addition of ULLE increased both cathodic and anodic overvoltages and caused mainly parallel displacement to the more negative and positive values, respectively relative to the blank curve. Thus, ULLE inhibitor influences both cathodic and anodic process, thereby inhibiting both cathodic hydrogen evolution and anodic mild steel dissolution. ULLE inhibitor has a greater effect on the cathodic than anodic polarization as a result of adsorption of the inhibitor molecule on mild steel surface [13]. The corrosion potential (E_{corr}) values shifted to less negative values by increasing the concentration of ULLE. Since the range of shift in E_{corr} values is 52.1 mV which is below ± 85 mV, the data suggested that ULLE acts as mixed type inhibitor [14]. The decrease in (I_{corr}) and the increase in inhibition efficiency (% IE) with increasing the inhibitor concentrations showed that the tested extracts acts as corrosion inhibitor for mild steel in 0.5 M H₂SO₄. The higher the values of (β_c) over those of (β_a) suggests that even though ULLE is a mixed type inhibitor, the cathodic reaction is the predominate factor.

3.2 Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS) Studies for Mild Steel Corrosion Inhibition

Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy curves for corrosion inhibition of mild steel in the absence and presence of different concentrations of the inhibitors ULLE is shown in Figure 2.

The corrosion behaviour of mild steel in the inhibited and uninhibited solution 0.5 M H₂SO₄ solution was investigated by EIS after immersion time of 30 minutes at 303 K. The Nyquist plot, Bode plot, phase angle plot and equivalent circuit diagram are presented in Figure 2. From Figure 2, it is clear that the diameter of Nyquist plot increases with ULLE concentration. Increase in the diameter of Nyquist plot in the presence of ULLE inhibitor indicated the corrosion inhibition of mild steel as a result of formation of inhibitive film on its surface [15].

Figure 2: EIS curves for mild steel in absence and presence of different concentration of ULLE (a) Nyquist plot (b) Bode plot (c) phase angle plot (d) equivalent circuit diagram

Table 2: Electrochemical Impedance parameters (EIS) for mild steel in 0.5 M H_2SO_4 solution in the presence and absence of the inhibitors.

Concentration (g/L)	R_s ($\Omega \text{ cm}^2$)	R_{po} ($\Omega \text{ cm}^2$)	$Q \times 10^{-5}$ ($\mu\Omega^{-1}\text{s}^n \text{ cm}^{-2}$)	n1	R_{ct} ($\Omega \text{ cm}^2$)	$C_{dl} \times 10^{-5}$ ($\mu\text{F cm}^{-2}$)	I.E %
0.0	6.3	-	50.0	0.81	14.53	-	-
0.2	5.9	8.0	4.9	0.83	386.4	4.8	96
0.6	6.3	7.9	4.4	0.89	762.1	4.1	98
1.0	6.3	7.9	3.5	0.98	984.5	3.2	99

Additionally, because the plots in the presence and absence of ULLE are identical, it shows that addition of the inhibitor does not change the corrosion mechanism significantly but only inhibits corrosion process by increasing the surface coverage by the adsorbed ULLE inhibitor [16]. The Nyquist plots were not perfect semicircles because of the inhomogeneity, roughness, impurities, or dislocations on the surface [17]. The EIS spectra show a single semicircle for a particular concentration of the inhibitor.

From the results presented in Table 2, the charge transfer resistance (R_{ct}) increased from 386.4 – 984.5 Ω cm^2 while the capacitance values of double-layer C_{dl} decreased 4.8 – 3.2 $\mu\text{F cm}^{-2}$ for ULLE with increasing concentration of the inhibitors from 0.2 – 1.0 g/L. The decrease in C_{dl} values with increase in concentration was due to the increase in the surface coverage by the inhibitors which resulted in an increase in the inhibition efficiency. The observed decrease in C_{dl} values, which normally corresponds to alteration of the double-layer thickness, can be attributed to the adsorption of the ULLE (with lower dielectric constant compared to the displaced adsorbed water molecules) on the metal/acid interface, thereby protecting the metals from the corrosive effect of the aggressive acids [18]. The corresponding parameters presented in Table 2 show that ULLE improves the magnitude of the R_{ct} , as well as the magnitude of the phase angle in the Bode plots, with a corresponding decrease in the value of Q .

As can be seen from the electrochemical results, increase in concentration of ULLE inhibitor increased both the inhibition efficiency and the surface coverage as of results of adsorption of the inhibitor on mild steel surfaces. Figure 3 shows the variation of inhibition efficiency with concentration of the inhibitor.

Figure 3: Variation of inhibition efficiency of ULLE for corrosion of MS in 0.5 M in H_2SO_4 with different inhibitor's concentration

3.3 UV-Visible Spectroscopy

The UV-Vis spectra of ULLE inhibitor and that of washing solution after immersion of mild steel at 333 K are shown in Figure 4. In the UV-Vis spectra, the presence of one or more peaks in the 200 to 400 nm region is an indication of the presence of unsaturated groups and functional groups with heteroatoms such as sulfur, nitrogen, and oxygen [19]. Figure 4a shows three peaks (peak 3, peak 4 and peak 5) while Figure 4b shows two peaks (peak 6 and Peak 7) in the 200 to 400 nm regions. In 400 to 800 region, five peaks are present in washing solution after immersion in mild steel (peaks 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5) while two peaks are in ULLE (peak 1 and 2).

Figure 4: Uv-Vis spectra of (a) ULLE inhibitor and (b) washing solution after immersion in mild steel at 333 K

3.4 Gas Chromatography – Mass Spectrophotometry (GC-MS)

The suggested compounds identified from the GC-MS results of ULLE inhibitor are presented in Table 3. Gas Chromatography - Mass spectrophotometric (GC-MS) analysis of ULLE revealed the presence of various compounds with unsaturated bonds, heteroatoms, cycloalkene and other functional groups as shown in Table 3. These compounds enhance the release of electrons from the inhibitors to the mild steel surface thereby resulting in corrosion inhibition of metals. It is observed from Table 3 that the most abundant natural compound identified in ULLE was cis-vaccenic acid as shown by its % peak area of 23.66%.

Table 3: Suggested compounds identified from GC-MS of ULLE

S/No	Name	Molecular formula	Molar (g/mol)	mass	Retention time (s)	% area	Peak
1.	Dodecanoic acid	C ₁₂ H ₂₄ O ₂	200		8.476	4.48	
2.	Tetradecanoic acid	C ₁₄ H ₂₈ O ₂	228		11.134	2.05	
3.	Methyl hexadecanoate	C ₁₇ H ₃₄ O ₂	270		12.949	1.38	
4.	n- Hexadecanoic acid	C ₁₆ H ₃₂ O ₂	256		13.488	18.23	
5.	p-Camphorene	C ₂₀ H ₃₂	272		13.823	2.25	
6.	Methyl-9,12-Octadecadienoate, (E, E) -	C ₁₉ H ₃₄ O ₂	294		15.270	1.10	
7.	Methyl -9- octadecenoate	C ₁₉ H ₃₆ O ₂	296		15.344	3.41	
8.	Methyl stearate	C ₁₉ H ₃₈ O ₂	298		15.710	0.81	
9.	Cis – Vaccenic acid	C ₁₈ H ₃₄ O ₂	282		16.201	23.66	
10.	Cis – 13-Octadecenoic acid	C ₁₈ H ₃₄ O ₂	282		16.260	14.17	
11.	Octadecanoic acid	C ₁₈ H ₃₆ O ₂	284		16.518	16.18	
12.	Linoelaidic acid	C ₁₈ H ₃₂ O ₂	280		16.778	5.83	
13.	Methyl(2Z) -isopropyl-5-methyl-2-hexenoate	C ₁₁ H ₂₀ O ₂	184		16.929	1.88	
14.	Oleic acid	C ₁₈ H ₃₄ O ₂	282		24.311	1.52	

3.5 Adsorption isotherm

Langmuir isotherm was used to analyze the adsorption of ULLE on to the mild steel surfaces. The Langmuir isotherm plots for PDP and EIS were shown in Figure 5 while the corresponding isotherm parameters obtained from the plots were shown in Table 4. The value of correlation coefficient (R^2) was used to determine the best fit. From Table 4, the inhibition process followed physical adsorption mechanism with Langmuir R-squared values of 0.9983 and 1.0000 for PDP and EIS respectively. The negative values of Gibb's free energy of adsorption process (ΔG_{ads}) which is less than 40 kJ/mol showed that the adsorption process is Physiosorption, feasible and spontaneous [20].

Figure 5: Langmuir Isotherm for adsorption of ULLE on Mild Steel surface

Table 4: Langmuir Isotherm Parameters

Electrochemical Technique	Slope	Intercept	K_{ads}	ΔG_{ads} (kJ/mol)	R^2
PDP	0.8347	-0.00064	1.0015	-10.123	0.9983
EIS	0.9810	0.00440	0.9899	-10.094	1

4. Conclusion

Leaves extracts of *Urena lobata* ULLE) were good corrosion inhibitor for mild steel 0.5 M H_2SO_4 . Potentiodynamic polarization studies revealed that the ULLE inhibitor exhibits mixed type inhibition mechanism on mild steel surfaces since the displacement of their E_{corr} values were all less than ± 85 mV with respect to the blank corrosion potential.

Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS) revealed that the charge transfer resistance (R_{ct}) increased while the double layer capacitance (C_{dl}) decreased with increasing inhibitors concentration. This was as a result of increased surface coverage due to adsorption of the inhibitors' phytochemical molecules on the mild steel surfaces leading to increased inhibition efficiency.

Gas Chromatography – Mass Spectrophotometric (GC-MS) studies revealed the presence of organic compounds in ULLE which were responsible for the extracts' ability to inhibit corrosion of mild steel.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they do not have any competing interest in the preparation and submission of this manuscript.

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